

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Stakeholder mapping template

Full resource

Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Stakeholder mapping template. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525686>

Table of contents

Introduction	2
Summary	2
Template as part of SCOPE+i Resources and in relation to SCOPE Framework	2
Stakeholder mapping	3

Introduction

Summary

This template supports identifying and documenting relevant stakeholders and to be filled out by relevant persons when starting a research assessment (RA) process. Depending on the process and organization relevant persons may vary. Identifying all stakeholders is important, as when truly completed, RA requires a wide range of diverse perspectives, expertises and experiences. In the template, stakeholders can be presented by stakeholder categories like administration or human resources.

Explore also Guide for assembling an assessment team <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525548> for identifying relevant expertises in a RA process.

Template as part of SCOPE+i Resources and in relation to SCOPE Framework

The [SCOPE+i Resources](#) aim to facilitate the transition towards Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) with particular focus on contributions to OS. Being one out of 17 resources (guides, templates and checklists), this template supports the structured organization of research assessment process and information from initial planning through to the publication of assessment protocols.

[SCOPE Framework](#) is a five-stage model for evaluating responsibly. It is a practical step-by-step process designed to help research managers, or anyone involved in conducting research evaluations, in planning new evaluations as well as check existing evaluations. SCOPE is an acronym, where S stands for START with what you value, C for CONTEXT considerations, O for OPTIONS for evaluating, P for PROBE deeply, and E for EVALUATE your evaluation. This template is most relevant for stages S and C.

Figure 1. SCOPE Framework by INORMS (2023) (modified by highlighting the most relevant stages for this resource).

More about SCOPE Framework in International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

All SCOPE+i Resources are brought together in the [GraspOS Infrastructure](#) (i), a simple, user-friendly interface (UI) where you can explore project results and save documents to learn and share with others.

Stakeholder mapping

Fill in the form below answering the questions about stakeholders. In the form there are suggestions about stakeholder categories. Leave boxes that do not apply empty. Add new rows if needed.

What is the working title of the research assessment process:

List of stakeholders of your RA process

Stakeholder category	Stakeholder's title, name and affiliation	Role(s) and activities in the assessment
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> e.g. evaluator, coordinator, data provider e.g. reporting, decision making
Researchers		
Management Research managers Administration		
Human resources Recruiting team Recruitment selection committee		
Bibliometricians Information specialists Librarians		
Experts in teaching and learning		
Research funders		

Cite as: Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Stakeholder mapping template. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525686>

Indexing services		
Metrics providers		
Service providers		
Ministry		
Government		
Research organizations		
National stakeholders		
Coalitions & initiatives		
Other stakeholders		

References

International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

Cite as: Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Stakeholder mapping template. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525686>

